

A tutorial on LiDAR data visualization and understanding for autonomous vehicles

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Abstract—LiDAR forms an important sensor in autonomous mobility due to its source of illumination. It provides better depth and details of the surroundings. This document helps users understand how LiDAR works, the types of LiDAR, and how the data is acquired and stored. To support interested participants in further exploration, most of the publicly available datasets are listed along with different toolboxes. Some of the labeling platforms, manuals, and readily available exercise links are included. An example to extract the road markings is explained in detail.

Index Terms—LiDAR, lane marking.

I. INTRODUCTION

Section-II in this paper explains about the the physics behind lasing and principle of operation of the LiDAR. Section-III briefs about the types of LiDAR, data acquisition in LiDARs and different ways by which the data can be stored. Section-IV provides the information on readily available automotive LiDAR datasets, toolboxes and data annotation tools. Section-V lists the available excercises on LiDAR data. Section-VI provides detailed example of road lane detection using LiDAR data, with the overview of existing methods.

II. INTRODUCTION ON LiDARS

A. Principle of Laser

A laser is an optical device that produces a high-intensity narrow beam of light through the process named Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation. The main steps involved in the working of laser are the absorption of radiation, spontaneous emission and stimulated emission.

The electrons at the lower energy state absorb energy from the external source and jump into the higher energy state. The electrons in the excited state are unstable, and they fall into the lower energy state quickly by releasing energy in the form of light. The light emitted due to this spontaneous emission will spread into the space.

The process by which electrons in the higher energy state are stimulated to emit light is termed as stimulated emission. Here, the external photons will directly interact with the higher energy state electrons and bring them to the lower energy state by emitting light. The light emitted with stimulated emission will travel larger distances without spreading in space.

Fig. 1. Laser principle

B. What is LiDAR? and its usage in an autonomous vehicle?

LiDAR is a sensing technology that employs laser pulses to measure the distance, size and other attributes of an object. LiDAR stands for **Light Detection and Ranging**. The light is delivered from a source and reflected from the scene's objects in LiDAR. The receiver at LiDAR detects the reflected light, and the time of flight technique is utilized to construct a distance-based representation of the scene's objects.

LiDARs have higher resolution, and provide better precision in range measurements when compared to radar. Currently, autonomous vehicles use LiDAR for Odometry, object detection and tracking, road sign detection, traffic signal identification, road border estimations, road lane detections, and to develop HD maps.

C. Principle of operation of the LiDAR

A sensor detects the reflection of a coherent light beam targeted at an object. The intensity and angle (or phase) of the beam are measured, and these values are entered into an equation that is executed by fast onboard chips to determine the position and properties of the reflecting item. A 3D "picture" of the surrounding region can be built by "sweeping" the beam and receiver array. This is depicted as a "point cloud" to assist us in visualizing what the LiDAR is "seeing".

LiDAR is composed of (a) Transmitter/emitter: It is composed of a laser that produces light in the wavelength range of 250 to 1600 nanometers (nm) (b) A detector: This is responsible for gathering, analyzing and computing the returned signal. The receiver typically consists of: (i) a photon-collecting telescope (ii) an optical analyzer that selectively filters wavelengths or polarization components and converts the light into an electrical signal. (c) beam steering

devices, and (d) a data acquisition unit that determines the elapsed pulse time and records the corresponding data [1]. There are 2 ways of performing LiDAR measurements:

a) ToF (Time of Flight) measurement

Many collimated light beams are emitted sequentially in short time intervals, These beams get reflected by the obstacle and sensed by the detector. Distance to the reflective object is calculated as a function of the speed of light, and duration of laser pulse from when it is emitted, reflected, and recaptured. Assuming that, the emitter and the detector are co-located, the laser pulse travels to the object and back within the time of flight (ToF).

$$R = c\tau/2 \quad (1)$$

Where, R- range, c- velocity of light, τ -the duration for the laser to make a to-and-fro trip to the object.

Pros: High data reliability and can be implemented with inexpensive laser sources.

Cons: Power limitations due to eye-safety regulations (large MEMS mirrors can be used as a work around).

b) FMCW technique

The emitted laser beam is chirp-modulated, so the frequency of the signal is changed within a chirp period. When an emitted laser beam finds an obstacle it gets reflected. This reflection affects the frequency of the light compared to the frequency at the reference. Reflected signal at the detector is mixed with the reference and the difference in frequency is measured. This intermediate frequency is proportional to the distance and velocity of the reflecting object. Further processing is done to extract object position and speed.

Pros: Good accuracy in target speed and position measurement, SNR, reduced power consumption and built-in ability to reject background light and environmental disturbances [2].

Performance Matrices of a LiDAR: Wavelength of Emitter, Field of View, Maximum detection range, Distance resolution, Angular resolution, precision, pulse rate, accuracy, scan rate, frame rate and Laser safety.

Factors affecting laser beams: Attenuation/Scattering through the atmosphere.

For more details on LiDAR for autonomous driving [3].

III. TYPES OF LiDAR

1) *Mechanical LiDAR:* LiDAR systems that use a rotating emitter and detector are classified as mechanical LiDARs. In these devices, both components are motorized and rotate through 360°, covering a full 2π radian field of view (FOV). The horizontal point cloud density depends on the emission rate of each optical unit and the speed of rotation of the optical assembly, while the vertical density is determined by the number of optical units included in the system.

2) *Hybrid solid state LiDARs :* The emitter and detector do not move; instead, the direction of the beams is controlled by adjustable optical elements such as micro-electro-mechanical

systems (MEMS), Risley prisms, Flash LiDAR, or optical phased arrays (OPA).

MEMS scanning system provides a wide FOV and micro-motion unit. In Risley prism scanners, the beam is steered using at least two wedge prisms that rotate in sequence, and the relative rotation speeds of the prisms define the scanning pattern.

In flash LiDARs, the emitter usually consists of an array of laser diodes to enhance scanning density within the FOV. These LiDARs systems illuminate the full field of view at

TABLE I
TYPES OF 3D-LiDARS USED IN AN AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

LiDAR Types			Manufacturer
Scanning	Mechanical (Pulsed)	Macro-Mechanical	Valeo SCALA1 Velodyne AlphaPrime Ouster OS-2
		MEMS	Hesai Pioneer Luminar LeiShen Blickfeld AEye AE1110 Robosense Innoviz InnovizPro Innovusion’s Falcon
	Non-mechanical	Optical phased array	Robosense RSLiDAR32 Quanergy S3-8 Blackmore
Non Scanning	Flash LiDAR		Argo Continental Xenomatrix LeddarTech Ibeo Innovusion Lumotive ZKW group Opsys Quanergy Ouster Cepton

once through the use of projecting lenses. Focal plane array (FPA) measures the ToF from received reflections. The angular resolution depends on the pixel density of the detector, and flash LiDAR receivers are organized in a matrix layout.

A. Data acquisition

Since mechanical LiDAR sensors have most established techniques and provide 360°field of view, most of the autonomous vehicles use rotor-based mechanical LiDAR for perception.

1) *A short note on Velodyne LiDAR:* [4] This is a mechanical LiDAR, where motor speed and scan time govern the azimuth angle, each laser beam has a fixed vertical angle. Every range reading is represented by $P_{ij} = (\rho_{ij}, \phi_i, \theta_j)$ where, i corresponds to a given laser beam, and j indicates the azimuth angle index.

The VLP-16 is an intelligent sensor with an internal processor and network interface. It provides data via Ethernet

using the UDP protocol. The sensor has 16 vertically stacked channels, each with a transmitter/receiver pair, giving a vertical field of view of 30°, which results in a 2° angular separation between consecutive beams. The lasers rotate 360° around the vertical axis, producing a full horizontal scan. This configuration allows the device to capture up to 300,000 points per second. Experimentally determined maximum measurement distance is 130 m.

Every laser has a distinct angular offset from the vertical axis and follows the specific laser firing sequence. This arrangement prevents cross-talk or interference and stores the range measurements in a predefined data buffer (range image), enabling quick access to each point and its neighboring points. The sensor can be set to provide single return (Strongest or last) or dual returns. The data packages from a VLP sensor consist of the following elements:

- 1) The 3D measurements captured by the sensor
- 2) The calibrated surface reflectivity corresponding to the returning light pulse
- 3) A collection of azimuth angles
- 4) A 4-byte timestamp
- 5) Two factory bytes that identify the mode of operation and sensor model.

The sensor provides information about objects in spherical coordinates, where r represents the radius, ω the height, and α the azimuth, this will be converted to a cartesian coordinate. A data block contains 100 bytes of binary information, including a two-byte flag (0xFFEE), a two-byte azimuth value, and 32 data points. Each measurement obtained from a single laser channel is referred to as a data point, which collectively forms the point cloud. One byte of the calibrated reflectivity and two bytes of distance represent a data point. The range is represented as an unsigned integer, and calibrated reflectivity values are reported on a scale from 0 to 255.

Flag bytes indicate the start of the data stream followed by azimuth, range values. The least significant data byte (little-endian) is transmitted first in case of azimuth and range measurements, this requires swapping of bytes while arriving at the actual value.

Conversion to Cartesian coordinate system:

The 3D Cartesian coordinates (X, Y, Z) can be derived from the spherical measurements as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= R \sin(\alpha) \cos(\omega) \\ Y &= R \cos(\alpha) \cos(\omega) \\ Z &= R \sin(\omega) \end{aligned}$$

2) *LiDAR data storage formats* : LiDAR data can be stored in multiple formats as listed in III.

- **.bin file** : This data format contains stream of bytes and the program shall be instructed on how to read the data. General structure of the .bin file is depicted below:

TABLE II
GENERAL STRUCTURE OF A .bin FILE

Header Instruction + Metadata	Data Continuous stream of bytes
-------------------------------	---------------------------------

```
# .PCD v.7 - Point Cloud Data file format
VERSION .7
FIELDS x y z rgb
SIZE 4 4 4 4
TYPE F F F F
COUNT 1 1 1 1
WIDTH 213
HEIGHT 1
VIEWPOINT 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
POINTS 213
DATA ascii
0.12543 0.78412 0 4.0000e+06
0.23455 0.67291 0 4.1000e+06
0.31789 0.59123 0 4.2000e+06
0.41234 0.51278 0 4.3000e+06
0.49876 0.43910 0 4.4000e+06
0.58921 0.37102 0 4.5000e+06
0.67345 0.30897 0 4.6000e+06
```

Fig. 2. PCD file format

TABLE III
DIFFERENT LIDAR DATA FORMATS

Format	Description
LAS(LASer)	x, y, z positions , intensity, return index, number of returns, scan direction indicator, classification , R, G, B
ZLAS	Compressed version of LAS
PCD	x, y, z, rgb, size, type, count, width, height, viewpoint, DATA
h5	Metadata, Hierarchical format , heterogeneous data, user defined Attributes
bin	x, y , z
PyLAS	Python library for LAS file
PCAP	Return intensity, timestamp, distance, azimuth and laser identifier
ASCII/XYZ/ CSV/TXT	x,y,z, intensity, timestamp (flexible)
ply	x,y,z, point normals, mesh data, intensity, labels, instance ID
ROS bag	point cloud data, intensity, timestamp, ring ID, return type

- **.pcd file**: A snapshot of PCD(Point Cloud Data) data format is given in Fig. 2.

The header section of the .pcd file contains file version number, field names , size and type of the data that is being stored. 'Count' indicates the number of elements in each dimension. 'Width' specifies count of points in a point cloud (in unorganized datasets) or in a row (in a matrix form dataset). 'Height' parameter provides an information if the point cloud is organized(provides total number of rows in an organized dataset) or not(default value-1). The 'Data' field in the header indicates the types of data that are supported.

- **.h5 file** : Utilized to store large, complex and heterogeneous data. The data is stored in well- organized manner, which helps quick retrieval and analysis.

IV. AUTOMOTIVE LiDAR DATASETS AND TOOLS

Some of the freely available, ready-to-use datasets, along with respective download links are provided in IV.

TABLE IV
SOME OF THE FREELY AVAILABLE AUTOMOTIVE LiDAR DATASETS

Dataset name	Download links
NUSCENES	https://www.nuscenes.org/download
iQumulus	iQumulus
KITTI	http://www.semantic-kitti.org/
Lyft	Lyft 3D recognition
K-LANE	https://github.com/kaist-avelab/K-Lane
H3D Honda 3D Dataset	H3D dataset
Audi Autonomous Driving Dataset (A2D2)	https://registry.opendata.aws/aev-a2d2/
Toronto-3D	Toronto-3D dataset
ApolloScape	Appolloscape Detection and Tracking
Pandaset	Pandaset
Waymo	https://waymo.com/open/data/perception
Argoverse 2	Argoverse dataset
Paris-Lille-3D	https://npm3d.fr/paris-lille-3d
Sydney Urban Objects	Sydney urban objects
DENSE Seeing Through Fog	https://light.princeton.edu/datasets/automated_driving_dataset/
Leeddar PixSet	Leeddar PixSet
Winter Adverse Driving dataSet (WADS)	https://digitalcommons.mtu.edu/wads/
Boreas	Boreas Dataset download instructions
RADIATE	https://pro.hw.ac.uk/radiate/downloads/
Oakland	Oakland dataset
Canadian Adverse Driving Conditions Dataset	http://cadcd.uwaterloo.ca/

A. Tool boxes

There are different tool boxes developed to process LiDAR data. Libraries along with input data types and purpose are listed in V.

B. Data annotation tools

Labeled data makes the training process much more efficient. Some of the multi-sensor/ single sensor labeling platform is listed in VI.

V. READILY AVAILABLE EXERCISES ON LiDAR DATA

A tutorial on **nuscenes** dataset: 15 hour driving data of two geographical areas are captured with 1 LiDAR, 5 RADARs, 6 cameras, IMU, GPS and is available with devkit. This tutorial walks the user through how to utilize automotive sensor's data. nuScenes devkit tutorial

VI. DETAILED EXAMPLE OF ROAD LANE DETECTION USING LiDAR DATA

A. Overview of existing techniques to identify the road lanes

Approaches used for detecting road lanes are depicted in Fig. 3. Some of the readily available exercises on LiDAR based road lane detection are listed in VII. Short notes on

TABLE V
TOOL BOXES LIBRARY DETAILS

Name	Platform	input datatype	Purpose
laspy	Python	las or laz	read/write
PyLAS	Python	las,laz	exchange 3D point data
Whitebox	Python	las	populate data
pyLidar	Python	SPD formats (V3,V4), RIEGL RXP, LVIS, LAS, Pulsewaves and ASCII.	Data processing
pcl	Python	list of tuples, a numpy array (1-D or 2-D), Point-Cloud, structured data or a ROS message	point cloud processing
pypcd	Python	pcd	point cloud processing
LiDAR toolbox	MATLAB	pcap,pcd, las,lbeo,ply	Design, analyze, and test processing
Open 3D	Python/C++	ply, pcd, xyz, txt	Visualization, processing, ML-ready point clouds

TABLE VI
DATA ANNOTATION TOOLS

Labeling platform	Links for the tool
Multisensor SuperAnnotate	https://segments.ai/superannotate
pointcloud Sama	https://www.novellic.com/automotive-annotation/sama
MindKosh	mindkosh
Dataloop	https://dataloop.ai/platform/lidar/
Custom-built	https://github.com/songanz/3D-LiDAR-annotator
CVAT	https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat
Scalabel	https://github.com/scalabel/scalabel

different methods are explained in the following section.

B. Literature review on road lane detection techniques

[5] LiDAR Intensity Calibration for Road Marking Extraction

- A 3D VLP-16 LiDAR and a 2D SICK LMS-511 LiDAR are mounted on the vehicle, positioned on the left and right sides. LiDAR intensity calibration process is described on the LiDAR data that was collected using Velodyne's VLP-16 at a rate of 10 Hz.
- The intensity calibration is based on the principle that same object shall possess same intensity value. The road markings with similar reflectivity can lead to variations in intensity values based on the distance and angle at which the surface is encountered. Correction to the intensity value is done by considering the effect of reflectance, range and incident angle.

TABLE VII
EXAMPLES OF ROAD LANE DETECTION ON LIDAR DATA

Platform	Example link
MATLAB	https://in.mathworks.com/help/lidar/ug/lane-detection-in-3d-lidar-point-cloud.html
Python	https://github.com/chiragkhandhar/Object-detection-in-Point-Cloud-Lane-Marking
Python	https://github.com/Lukas-Justen/Lane-Marking-Detection
Python	https://github.com/Livox-SDK/livox_lane_detection
Python	https://github.com/binbli/Lane-Marking-Quality-Assessment PC Lane Marking Detection

- Intensity calibration of each sensor concerning the reference surface (wall) is exploited and reflectance of the surface is estimated, the mean and variance of the intensity are recorded in a lookup table.
- LiDAR intensity model is expressed as a function of incidence angle and distance $f(i, d)$.

$$I_{id} \propto \frac{\rho \cos(\theta_i)}{d^2} = \rho f(i, d) \quad (2)$$

where 'd' represents the distance, ' θ_i ' denotes the angle of incidence and ρ corresponds to surface reflectivity. The proportion between the intensity values of two surfaces measured at identical incidence angles and distances should correspond to the true reflectance ratio of these surfaces. Given that the intensity behavior of a reference surface, I_{ref} , is known for each angle θ_i and distance, the reflectance ρ of another surface can be calculated by comparing its intensity value I_{id} to the reference characteristics. This estimated reflectance is used as a calibrated intensity value.

$$\frac{I_{id}}{I_{ref}} \propto \frac{\rho f(i, d)}{\rho_{ref} f(i, d)} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_{ref}} \quad (3)$$

$$\rho \propto \rho_{ref} \frac{I_{id}}{I_{ref}} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. Overview of road lane Identification techniques

- Reference surface data acquisition
3D LiDAR measurements were collected from the exterior wall, and the angle of incidence θ_i for each point was determined by computing its surface normal. The lookup table (LUT) was constructed with a resolution of 1° for θ_i and 1cm for the distance to the surface. Using this information, the LUT was generated by calculating the average value μ_{id} and standard deviation σ_{id} of the intensity associated with each incidence angle i and distance 'd' from the surface.
When both the distance and the angle of incidence are small, the measured intensity tends to be high, accompanied by a large standard deviation. As the distance increases, the intensity decreases along with its standard deviation. Consequently, for points that coincide at the same location after calibration, the standard deviation can be used to weigh those points with higher reliability.

$$\mu_{id} = \frac{\sum I_{id}}{N} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{id} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (\mu_{id} - I_{id})^2}{N}} \quad (6)$$

N- nu of data corresponding to each table element. the mean value from the LUT is taken as the intensity of the reference surface I_{ref} .

- Intensity calibration filtering
After the calibration, the brightness of distant road markings resemble those of nearby road markings, which may cause noise due to
(a) When the distance and angle of incidence (θ_i) are large, the contrast between the intensity of road markings and the surrounding asphalt diminishes. Under these conditions, measurement errors in the sensor's intensity values can introduce noise into the data.
(b) Inaccurate calculation of the incidence angle or sensor distance errors.
Voxel filtering is applied based on the calibrated intensity and each point's standard deviation of as depicted in equations (7) and (8)
n represents the number of points contained within a single voxel

$$\mu = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\mu_k}{\sigma_k^2}}{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_k^2}} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_k^2}}} \quad (8)$$

- Validation is done through Otsu's method.

[6] Modeling Laser Intensities For Simultaneous Localization and Mapping

- “Surface reflectivity, measured independently of pose, was obtained from data collected by the SICK LMS 291-S05 and Hokuyo UTM-30LX sensors, and modeled as a data-driven representation of laser intensity.
- Approximation for Lambertian reflector is formulated as,

$$I \propto P \propto \frac{\rho \cos(\theta_i)}{r^2} \quad (9)$$

This formula breaks at a shorter distance, termed as the ‘near distance effect’.

- Two models were created to evaluate how intensity changes with ‘r’ and ‘ θ_i ’.
- The variation of intensity modeled independently as

$$I \propto P \propto \rho f(r) f(\theta_i) \quad (10)$$

where $f(r)$ and $f(\theta_i)$ represent the data-driven estimates defining the effect on intensities, ρ is a surface reflectivity. The second approach involves developing a model as,

$$I \propto P \propto \rho f(r, \theta_i) \quad (11)$$

where $f(r, \theta_i)$ captures the combined effect of r and θ_i on intensity variation.

- The angle of incidence is determined by computing the dot product between the direction of the laser beam and the local surface normal. The surface normal is obtained as the eigenvector associated with the smallest eigenvalue of the covariance matrix, which is calculated using neighboring points around a given location. Since the accuracy of normal estimation depends on point cloud density, it degrades in sparser regions. As a result, reliable intensity characteristics can only be obtained for incidence angles up to $\theta_i \leq 80^\circ$ at shorter distances and up to and $\theta_i \leq 60^\circ$ at greater distances.
- Assumption is $f(r, \theta_i)$ varies in the same manner for all the surfaces for a given scanner, and this helps to ignore any coupling between f and ρ .

A relative measure of the surface reflectivity is obtained as,

$$\frac{I_{rec}}{I_{ref}} \propto \frac{P_{rec}}{P_{ref}} \propto \frac{\rho f(r, \theta_i)}{\rho_{ref} f(r, \theta_i)} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_{ref}} = \tilde{\rho} \quad (12)$$

- For $f(r, \theta_i)$ a scattered interpolant (with linear interpolation) is used to interpolate the values a look-up table is generated.
- The grid structure is generated with the occupancy probability $P(\text{gi})$ and the surface reflectivity measure $R(\text{gi})$. In this work, the reflectivity for each grid cell is computed using a straightforward incremental averaging approach.
- An evaluation of the developed approach ignores the effect of r, θ_i : (a) The raw model- ignore the effect of r and θ_i and consider only Intensity (b) The ‘range model’- consider the effect of ‘r’ and systematically ignore θ_i effect and then correct Intensity. Quantitative evaluation is also performed by comparing with alternate methods. Valuations indicate that, the variation of reflectivity observed in ‘r’ in one of the surfaces

and both in ‘r’ and θ_i in another; The evaluation concludes external parameter correction is required. Intensity increment plots are observed to be different for both sensors.

- In situations where the estimation of surface normals is unreliable for most sensor observations due to sparse point density, incorporating surface attributes such as reflectivity or color along with geometric information can improve the approach.

[7] Unsupervised Calibration for Multi-beam Lasers

- This study aims to estimate optimal parameters for each beam’s orientation and distance response, along with a probabilistic generative model describing the remittance behavior for surfaces with different reflectivity. The experiment is performed on independently collected, accumulated data of a few seconds.
- No calibration target is used, assumption is made such that, points in space are typically distributed along continuous surfaces. The sensor’s extrinsic pose(translation and rotation) relative to the robot’s coordinate frame is recovered while addressing intrinsic (beam level) information.
- An energy function is introduced on the point cloud, which imposes a penalty on points that deviate from surfaces determined by points from other beams. By collecting points across multiple sensor poses, derivatives of this energy function are computed with respect to individual parameters for pairs of beams. An iterative optimization procedure is then applied to arrive at a globally consistent calibration with very low error.

$$J = \sum_{b_i=1}^B \sum_{b_j=b_i-N}^{b_i+N} \sum_k w_k ||\eta_k(p_k - m_k)||^2 \quad (13)$$

Here, N represents the number of neighboring beams to which each beam is aligned, and B denotes the total number of beams, The index k iterates over the points observed by beam b_j , with p_k being the k^{th} point projected according to the current transformation. The point m_k is defined as the closest point to p_k observed by beam b_i , η_k is the surface normal m_k and w_k is 1 or 0 depending on whether $||p_k - m_k|| < d_{max}$.

- For each optimization of translation and rotation parameters grid search is utilized, This compares the current energy score with the result produced when the variables are adjusted together in every possible direction.
- A Bayesian generative model for each beam’s response to surfaces with different reflectivity is constructed using the Expectation-Maximization algorithm. The intensity return from beam is modeled.
- In the Maximization step, the most probable beam parameters are determined based on the observed data and the current intensity distributions for each map cell. First, the likelihood of each map cell exhibiting all possible intensity values is calculated using the observed

intensity returns from each beam and the distributions over intensity values computed during the E-step. Next, Bayes' theorem is applied to estimate the distribution of potential intensity returns for each beam, given the intensity distributions of the map cells. Once the Expectation-Maximization process converges, a fully generative model is obtained that describes each beam's response to surfaces with varying reflectivity in the environment.

[8] Advanced point cloud processing

- This paper focuses on remote sensing/airborne laser scanning point cloud or GPS-based mobile laser scanner. The point cloud is divided into planar surfaces through a 3D Hough transform, and plane parameters are estimated using a surface-growing algorithm.
- Rooftops and Roadsides identification is performed, terrain surface segmentation is done to small planes, road markings are identified with a mobile scanner, ie. by making use of the reflection strength of a laser scanner. This method is observed to have a better appearance from the top view.
- This study introduces a method for detecting lane markings from point clouds using range-dependent intensity thresholding based on normalized reflectance. The detected marker points are subsequently grouped through connected component analysis, and the complete outlines of the lane markings are reconstructed by fitting predefined shapes to these segments.

[9] Lane width estimation in work zones using LiDAR-based mobile mapping systems

- This paper presents a method for estimating lane width using LiDAR point clouds. A mobile mapping system along with the trajectory elevation information is utilized to acquire geometrically calibrated and accurate point clouds.
- Lane markings are detected using intensity data. The center lines are clustered to locate missing or unclear markings, and unambiguous markings are used to estimate lane width. These estimates help identify narrow, wide, or ambiguous lane regions.
- Extraction of the road surface and removal of outliers for lane marking involves trajectory information and map information, IMU information is utilized for surface extraction. The lane width estimation method uses intensity data from the 3D point cloud combined with trajectory information. Calibration is done with the help of GNSS.
- Lane markings are detected by analyzing the intensity histogram of the road surface. The threshold Th_I (Levinson and Thrun method) is defined at the 95th percentile, and points above this value are selected as potential lane markings due to their higher reflectivity.
- Details on road surface extraction

- A height threshold h_{IMU} , corresponding to the expected normal distance between the road surface and the IMU frame, is applied to select points belonging to the road.
- Select a random trajectory elevation point and find the LiDAR point (P_i) with the closest (X, Y) coordinates and lowest Z-coordinate. A k-nearest neighbor search is then used to define the road surface, followed by plane fitting to estimate its parameters
- The height threshold is calculated from the normal distance between the trajectory elevation point and the fitted plane. Along with h_{IMU} , an extra buffer h_{buff} is added to accommodate road slopes (around 2%) for drainage. LiDAR points within this buffer are classified as road surface points.
- Details on lane marking extraction
 - Create a distribution of intensity values for road surface points.
 - The road surface points in the top 5% of the intensity frequency distribution are considered potential lane markings.

[10] Leveraging LiDAR Intensity to Evaluate Roadway Pavement Markings

- Comparative study of retro-reflectivity device and LiDAR for road marking identification and accuracy evaluation on a collected dataset.
- GNSS and INS data are used to georeference remote sensing images and measurements. Road marking extraction techniques can be grouped into two main types: (a) methods based on LiDAR point clouds and (b) methods using LiDAR intensity images.
- Height buffer-based strategy used for selecting the road surface points. Lane markings follows below steps include (i) thresholding using the top 5% of intensity values, (ii) removing outliers along scan lines, (iii) clustering based on point density [66] (iv) eliminating geometric outliers, and (v) applying local and global refinement.
- Conclusion- The patterns observed in standard and infrared retroreflective measurements closely match the LiDAR intensity readings at corresponding points.

[11] Learning Hierarchical Features for Automated Extraction of Road Markings From 3-D Mobile LiDAR Point Cloud

- Point clouds acquired from Riegl VMX-450. First, road surface points are separated from the raw point cloud using an approach that relies on curb information.
- The roadway was first segmented into sections following the path of movement. These sections were then further divided into smaller units based on their sideways distance from the path. Within each unit, road markings were identified by applying Otsu's thresholding technique. Any points that were incorrectly labeled were subsequently identified and filtered out using their distinguishing properties. Road marking points were then classified into

specific categories(edge lines, stop lines, zebra crossing lines, arrow markings, rectangular markings, and centerlines) using the following steps: (1) Clustering based on euclidean distance, (2) segmenting mixed-marking clusters using a voxel-driven normalized cut approach, and (3) classifying markings through trajectory cues, deep learning techniques, and PCA.

- **Road Surface Segmentation** Curb points are identified based on elevation gradient and are used as road boundary
- **Multi-segment thresholding** To limit the effects of uneven intensity during road marking extraction, a normalization step is applied. For each segment, point intensities are scaled to a grayscale range of 0–255. An optimal threshold is then determined using Otsu’s method, which selects a value that maximizes the separation between classes relative to the variation within them. The corresponding between-class variance is expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_B^2 = \omega_R \omega_M (\mu_M - \mu_R)^2 \quad (14)$$

Here ω_R and ω_M represent the probabilities of the road surface and road marking classes, respectively; and the threshold is, $G = \text{argmax}_0 \leq G \leq 255 \sigma_B^2(G)$.

- **Spatial Density filtering** Due to the material properties and backscattered reflectance of the bituminous roads, there are areas of the road surface where the road markings’ intensities are comparable. To eliminate noise from the detected road markings, a filtering approach based on spatial density is introduced.

For a given point $p(x,y,z)$, its spatial density can be expressed as follows:

$$SD(p) = 1 + \sum_{p_i \in N(p)} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - x)^2 + (y_i - y)^2 + (z_i - z)^2}{(d_N/3)^2}\right) \quad (15)$$

Here, $N(p)$ refers to the neighboring set around point p , d_N indicates its size, and $p_i(x_i, y_i, z_i)$ represents points within this region. The density at a point is influenced by both the number of nearby points and how they are spatially arranged. Points surrounded by more neighbors exhibit higher density, whereas noise points tend to have lower density. After computing these values, points with density below a chosen threshold ρ_{SD} are identified as noise and removed.

[12] Lane Detection and tracking based on LiDAR data

- A 1D laser scanner is installed on the vehicle’s front bumper, angled downward towards the roadway. 2 strategies for lane detection are proposed; (a) one single scan at a time or ‘time-separate’ analysis (b) multiple scans collected over time or ‘a flexible temporal fusion’ of the scan data.
- Spatio-temporal fusion approach: For the reflectivity observations of all data points, the probability density function is obtained. Most points originate from the road surface, so the maximum observation in the probability density function or histogram represents the road’s reflectivity.

tivity.

$$r_{roadsurface} = \text{max}_r p(r[t])$$

- A dynamic threshold is determined from the highest value in the reflectivity PDF to enhance the distinction between lane markings and the road surface. The threshold is then adjusted using the standard deviation: values corresponding to the road surface within one standard deviation are removed from the histogram, and the resulting mean is recalculated to serve as the binarization threshold. Intensity values adjusted to one byte 0–255.
- To improve lane detection, the binary image is processed using the Canny edge detection algorithm. The lane model is assumed as Clothoid and lane tracking is done using Kalman filters.
- By transforming the view to a global perspective, the effects of the vehicle’s motion are minimized, allowing a comprehensive representation of the lane. The method ultimately outputs parameters that describe the road in terms of these global characteristics.
- The developed method can detect continuous as well as discontinuous lane markings.
- **Individual lane Detection** Vertical detection windows are formed within the map, which is structured as a grid with a variable number of rows m and a fixed number of columns n ($m \times n$). Assuming the vehicle is generally positioned near the center, two detection windows are offset to the left and right of the middle. At each step of this shift, the count of white pixels within the window is measured. When this count exceeds a threshold that depends on the vehicle’s speed, a lane is considered detected. Using multiple rows $m > 1$, past measurement is incorporated as well. Based on the current row, two windows ($m_2 \times n_2$, whereas $m_2 \ll m_1$) are shifted in a small region around the pre-detected lane markings. This proceeding ensures that the ultimate determination of a newly identified lane marking is made on a single-row basis (i.e. $m_2 = 1$) and is applied through a scan-by-scan process, but the past is incorporated as well. Consequently, measurement outliers are efficiently filtered. To support real-time processing, the areas used for pre-detection—based on the current scan and the previous $m_1 \times n_1$ region—along with the window size for the current frame $m_2 \times n_2$, can be adjusted. This approach helps reset any errors that may have accumulated over consecutive detections.

[13] Automated extraction of road features using LiDAR data: A review of LiDAR applications in transportation

This paper categorizes features into three main groups: a) on-road information, including the road surface, lane markings, and road edges; b) roadside objects, such as lamp posts, trees, and utility poles; and c) roadside and geometric information, which covers traffic signs, road cross-section data, vertical alignment, pavement condition monitoring, sight distance, and vertical clearance. Some details from the cited references are summarized in VIII.

TABLE VIII
SUMMARY OF ROAD SURFACE, LANE MARKING, AND ROAD EDGE EXTRACTION METHODS

Feature	Technique / Description [Reference]
Road Surface Extraction	[14] Models the road as connected planes and segments the surface into multiple planar sections. Each plane's center and heading are estimated using Kalman filtering, and planes are fitted with Random sample consensus. [15] Presents a fully automated extraction from mobile LiDAR: First ,defines the road trajectory,then detects surface and boundaries using height, mean, and variance. Local hypothesis tests remove false boundary points, ensuring accurate road surface identification.
Lane Marking and Road Edge Extraction	[16] CuTE method: combines camera, LiDAR, and onboard sensors to detect and track curbs. Uses nonlinear Markov switching to follow curbs accurately. [17]LiDAR-based road and edge detection: separates LiDAR data into elevation and ground-plane signals. Road regions are identified using elevation filtering, and edges are validated by comparing to a standard road model. The proposed method was validated in urban environments. [18]Road marking and curb extraction: LiDAR points classified into road markings and curbstones using image processing and triangulated irregular networks (TIN). [19]The method organizes LiDAR points along scan lines, identifies initial seed points, fits lines through them, smooths the intensity values, and applies edge detection (EDEC) to extract the road markings. It was tested on the Jincheng highway and achieved high accuracy.

[20] Use of mobile LiDAR in road information inventory: A review

This review paper is summarized in the table IX

[29] Using mobile laser scanning data for automated extraction of road markings

- An algorithm is proposed for lane marking extraction that uses thresholds varying with range and applies morphological operations. The data were acquired using the Riegl VMX-450 mobile mapping system.
- The road surface is extracted using a curb-based approach. The LiDAR data is divided into blocks perpendicular to the road trajectory to improve computational efficiency. Within each block, elevation differences are analyzed to separate points into layers and detect curbs, which define the edges of the road surface.
- Geo-referenced intensity images are created from LiDAR points using inverse-distance-weighted (IDW) interpolation. The road surface is rasterized based on point reflectivity and distance from the road center, and lane markings are extracted using a density-based multi-threshold method, followed by morphological closing to remove noise and fill gaps.
- The algorithm was tested on two datasets spanning 168m of roadway. Three sub-segments from these roads were manually compared to ground truth to assess performance. The evaluation measured the completeness (how many road markings were successfully extracted) and correctness (the proportion of extracted markings that were valid). The method achieved completeness and correctness rates of 0.96 and 0.83, respectively.

[30] Road marking detection using LiDAR reflective intensity data and its application to vehicle localization

- Authors developed a method that detects a wide variety of road markings directly from LiDAR reflectivity measurements. The approach begins with a calibration of LiDAR intensity returns to compensate for sensor

characteristics, followed by a segmentation of the road surface using a curb detector. Within this region, an intensity histogram is computed and analyzed using a variant of Otsu's thresholding, where the selected threshold maximizes the between-class variance of asphalt versus marking reflectivities. Statistics such as normalized intensity distributions, cumulative sums, and cumulative means support the threshold selection. The resulting marking points are then integrated into a Monte Carlo Localization framework, resulting in notable reductions in lateral localization error when compared to using curb data alone.

[38] Next Generation Map Making: Geo-Referenced Ground-Level LIDAR Point Clouds for Automatic Retro-Reflective Road Feature Extraction

- A profile-based intensity method was used to extract 3D lane markings directly from point clouds. The point clouds were first sliced along the trajectory, and road surfaces were identified using geometric cues from curbs, barriers, and borders. Lane markings were then located by detecting intensity peaks along each scan line. Compared to 2D image-based methods, this approach works directly on raw MLS data. It improves extraction completeness and correctness and preserves the geospatial information of road markings for further applications.

[40] Automatic inventory of road cross-sections from mobile laser scanning system

- Several lanes are identified from a road section using mobile LiDAR data. The method first separates the road surface using adaptive height thresholds and scan angles. Then, intensity-based filtering is used to detect lane markings. The false positives in estimated lane markings are removed by the application of a geometric filter. After this, Principal Component Analysis links broken line segments. Distances between lines help estimate lane width, shoulder width, and slope changes. The method

TABLE IX
LiDAR-BASED ROAD SURFACE, ROAD MARKING, AND ROAD STRUCTURE EXTRACTION METHODS

Feature	Technique / Description [Reference]
3D Road Surface Extraction	[21] Road lane identification using Hough transform on point clouds. Computationally intensive for large LiDAR datasets. [22] Fuzzy clustering based on maximum entropy theory combined with multi-time weighted least-squares linear fitting to segment linear and nonlinear point distributions. High computation time required. [23] Two-step local road shape extraction: RANSAC applied to individual scan lines for rough roadside estimation, followed by multi-frame accumulation for curb candidates.
Road Edge Extraction	[24] Road edges estimated using slope and standard deviation from LiDAR points. [25] Two-step strategy: generate lines from points and extract road edges using slope, intensity, pulse width, and vehicle proximity. [26] Curb edge extraction using derivatives of Gaussian applied to LiDAR points. [27] Modeled curbs based on elevation difference, point density, and slope changes using a moving window operator.
Data-Driven Road Surface Identification	[27] [28] [29] Road points are identified by combining several LiDAR attributes—like intensity, pulse width, height, slope, and average values—with prior road knowledge such as curb location, minimum road width, and elevation. [31] [32] [33] Individual LiDAR scan lines are processed to classify points into categories such as roads, buildings, and other urban objects. Any erroneous measurements are identified and handled appropriately. For accurate representation, volumetric modeling techniques are applied to both surface-structured objects (like roads and building facades) and volume-structured objects (such as trees).
2D/3D Feature Image-Based Extraction	[30] Road surfaces are identified from 3D LiDAR point clouds using a combination of differential, distance-based, and regression filters, enabling effective separation of road regions from nearby objects. Trajectory data used to reduce computational cost. [26], [15], [29] [34] For large volumes of mobile LiDAR data, converting 3D point clouds into 2D feature images provides a more efficient approach for road surface extraction using image processing techniques. [35] Road surfaces are extracted from rasterized LiDAR data (elevation, reflectance, and pulse width) using active contour (snake) models. [36] Multi-source LiDAR data (terrestrial and aerial) are combined, and road patches are generated using map-based splines. A ribbon snake (active contour) model is then applied to each patch to detect smooth road boundaries, and points within these boundaries are labeled as road points.
Road Surface Structures / Markings	[37] Semantic knowledge about road marking shapes and sizes is used to guide the extraction process. Building on this, a range of image processing techniques—such as thresholding, Hough Transform, morphological operations, and Multi-Scale Tensor Voting (MSTV)—are applied to 2D feature images derived from 3D LiDAR data [18], [38], [8], [23], [39], [28], [40], [41]. While these methods work well for standard markings, approaches like the Hough Transform are less effective for complex patterns, including hatchings and textual road markings. Intensity variations caused by the LiDAR scanning pattern can make road marking extraction challenging. To handle this, [8] explored the use of multiple thresholds that relate the scanning distance to intensity values. [29] introduced a dynamic approach where thresholds are adjusted according to local point density, and the results are refined using a morphological closing operation with a linear structuring element to improve marking. [41] Multi-Scale Tensor Voting (MSTV) enhances road marking extraction by reducing noise and capturing underlying marking patterns even in distorted data. [11] 3D point cloud-based automated marking extraction: Large markings are segmented using trajectory and curb information, while small markings are identified using deep learning and PCA. Finally, all markings are classified into categories such as boundary lines, stop lines, arrows, pedestrian crossings, zebra crossings, and centerlines.

was tested on two highways in Spain (400 m and 1 km). Changes in shoulder width were mainly caused by vehicles blocking the scanner’s view.

- The authors introduced a method to derive road cross-section details such as the number of lanes, road and shoulder widths, and superelevation from LiDAR point cloud data collected with an Optech LYNX system. First, points not belonging to the road were removed using a height-based filter that considered scan angle and sensor position. Then, a reference line for each cross section was created by fitting lines to the remaining road points, and any points too far from this line were discarded. Lane markings were detected by finding peaks in intensity along each scan line. The data was captured at high speed to keep clear gaps between scan lines. To reduce errors, distances between detected points

were checked, and unlikely points were removed. The remaining points were grouped based on proximity and labeled as left, right, or center lane markings. Finally, smooth curves were fitted to these groups, and lane widths were estimated using the detected markings and the road’s central axis.

[42] Reflectivity of pavement markings: Analysis of retroreflectivity degradation curves

- Authors investigated the degradation of pavement marking retroreflectivity by collecting intensity measurements with a vehicle-mounted retroreflectometer across approximately 80 test sections in Washington State. The study produced retroreflectivity degradation curves for common paint materials, showing how reflective intensity decreases over time and how quickly

markings may fall below minimum thresholds for nighttime visibility. The measurements also included different colored lanes made from water-based and solvent-based paints, with most markings exhibiting reflectivity values in the range of 50–250 mcd/m²/lux. However, variability in the data limited the creation of statistically robust predictive models.

[43] Automated road markings extraction from mobile laser scanning data

- The LiDAR data was transformed into 2D range and intensity representations. Range-dependent intensity thresholding was then applied to identify potential lane markings. Binary morphological operations were used to extract lane marking features. Knowledge of standard road marking dimensions was incorporated to refine the extracted shapes and suppress noise. Additionally, prior information (heading angle) on road boundaries was utilized to calculate linear structure element.
- Worn or missing road markings were restored using linear dilation. Known marking dimensions were then used with erosion to eliminate stray points and reduce noise from the dilation process.
- A dynamic multi-thresholding approach was first applied by analyzing how the scanning range relates to intensity values. This was followed by a morphological nearest-neighbor operation to better capture the linear structure of roads. Significant improvement was then achieved using the MSTV algorithm. Additionally, generating 2D GRF images from MLS data proved effective for extracting road markings, especially in handling intensity inconsistencies caused by different scanning patterns.
- A robust and automated method was used to extract road markings by applying distance-based thresholds to intensity values. This approach accounts for variations in reflected laser signals caused by changes in angle and range.

[44] Semi automated generation of road transition lines using mobile laser scanning data

- Experiments were carried out using geo-referenced intensity data from a Riegl VMX-450 mobile laser scanner. The workflow first isolates the road surface and then applies a multi-level thresholding method to extract road markings. These extracted markings are subsequently used to generate transition lines that represent the vehicle paths through intersections.
- The proposed approach is structured into three main stages: detecting the road surface, extracting lane markings, and generating transition lines. Road surface points are first isolated using a voxel-based upward-growing method combined with an enhanced region-growing process. Next, lane markings are derived through multi-level thresholding and geometric filtering. Finally, transition lines are produced by integrating a lane-node construc-

tion method with a cubic Catmull–Rom spline to create smooth vehicle paths.

- Candidate lane markings are first detected using multi-thresholding and Otsu-based threshold selection [11], followed by spatial density filtering to eliminate noise. Since the extracted marking points lack semantic structure or connectivity, clustering is required to distinguish actual lane markings. Assuming that points located close to each other belong to the same marking, Conditional Euclidean clustering is applied, and geometric filters are then used to refine and isolate the true lane-marking segments.

[45] Generation of horizontally curved driving lines in HD maps using mobile laser scanning point clouds

- Smooth horizontal driving paths are created from the extracted road markings by fitting them with a cubic-spline curve.
- A range of methods, including multi-threshold road marking extraction, georeferenced intensity imagery production, and statistical outlier removal, are applied to detect and extract the road markings. To improve the robustness and effectiveness of the road marking extraction, a refined multi threshold algorithm is proposed.
- For the road-marking extraction, inverse distance weighting and intensity information weighing is carried out. Higher weights are assigned for a point that has a) A greater intensity value and b) less distance to the center of the grid. A grid size of 4cm is used in this work to balance accuracy with computational efficiency. Multi-threshold and Otsus threshold methods are applied on georeferenced feature imagery. Data denoising is performed with the statistical outlier filtering tool provided by PCL.
- Assuming that the average point-to-neighbor distances follow a Gaussian distribution with mean μ and standard deviation σ , any point falling outside the chosen range is treated as noise and removed from the road-marking point cloud.

[46] Combined lane mapping using a mobile mapping system

- The LiDAR data used in this study was obtained from a Velodyne HDL-32 sensor. The work presents three main contributions: an intensity-correction approach that reduces reflectivity variations on road-surface points, an adaptive thresholding technique for accurately detecting lane markings, and a texture-based saliency analysis applied to MMS images to enhance the reliability and robustness of lane-level mapping.
- The literature review in this work outlines different methods used to extract road surfaces directly from raw point-cloud data as i) Planar surface-based methods that use Hough transforms and RANSAC followed by model fitting algorithms and ii) Edge-based methods that segment the road surface using linear road borders that have first been detected and fitted. Many of these

road-extraction methods are computationally heavy and take considerable time to run. Features like surface normals and height differences are often used to identify road boundaries or curbs. To speed up processing, several approaches rely on scan lines, grid structures, or voxel representations. Using vehicle trajectory data can further accelerate road-edge detection by limiting the search to regions perpendicular to the path. For lane-mark extraction, inconsistent intensity values pose a challenge, as a single global threshold can lead to missing markings or generating false detections. Multi-threshold methods to avoid this inconsistency were introduced in [43], [29], [11]. 2D feature images derived from the 3D point cloud are explored in [43], [29] to detect and extract road markings.

- **Road-surface extraction:** Using elevation statistics and trajectory information, the abrupt shift in the normal vector of the gridded point clouds is used, to detect the curb grids on each side of the trajectory. Curb grids are used to segment the road points and fit the road boundaries. To make the next lane extraction process easier, the road points' inconsistent reflecting intensity is adjusted.
- **Intensity correction of road points** Measured intensity of the LiDAR points is expressed as,

$$LI = C \cdot \sum_{i=0}^N (\eta_i \cdot R^i) \quad (16)$$

In this model, LI represents the measured LiDAR intensity, R is the range, η_i are the polynomial coefficients for a polynomial of degree N. The term C includes additional constant factors. Coefficients η_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are estimated using least-square fitting on the road-surface points. Based on the minimum mean-square error, a third-degree polynomial ($N=3$) was selected for the experiments. The corrected intensity is then computed as:

$$LI_R = LI \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (\eta_i \cdot R_S^i)}{\sum_{i=0}^N (\eta_i \cdot R^i)} \quad (17)$$

where R_S is the average range of the road points.

- **Lane-marking extraction:** The process involves three main stages. First, the refined 3D road points are projected onto a 2D intensity image to establish a 3D-to-2D correspondence. Next, an adaptive thresholding technique is applied to produce a binary image that highlights the lane markings. Finally, a shape-based analysis is performed to remove incorrect or misleading negative detections.
- **Lane mapping:** In each local segment, the extracted lane markings are fitted to form continuous lane lines. To assess the intensity contrast near these lane lines within MMS images, a LiDAR-guided textural saliency approach is introduced. Additionally, a global post-processing step is applied to recover lane lines that

may be missing due to localized occlusions.

[47] Mobile laser scanned point-clouds for road object detection and extraction: A review

- The paper summarizes several widely used open-access datasets: Paris-rue-Madame dataset, Paris-Lille-3D dataset, TUM City Campus MLS point cloud dataset, Ford Campus Vision and LiDAR Data Set, North Campus Long-Term Vision and LiDAR Dataset, KITTI Vision Benchmark Suite, Cityscapes Datasets, Large-scale Point Cloud Classification Benchmark dataset.
- The road surface and road marking extraction methods listed by the authors are provided in X XI .

[48] Multi channel LiDAR processing for lane detection and estimation

The difference in reflectivity between the road surface and the painted markings is used to distinguish lane lines. An adaptive thresholding approach is introduced, which extracts lane markings by minimizing the within-class variance of the reflectivity values.

[49] Using Road Pavement Markings as Ground Control for LiDAR Data

A global threshold was selected based on the intensity distribution within a defined search window. To evaluate the positional accuracy of ALS data, road markings were treated as ground control features. GPS survey measurements collected along the pavement helped determine appropriate search windows for locating lane markings in the LiDAR data. The road markings were then extracted by applying an intensity-based threshold, and the results were compared with the GPS survey data to assess the accuracy of the LiDAR points.

[50] A mobile mapping system for road data capture based on 3D road model

The authors first addressed intensity inconsistencies by applying a scan-angle-rank-based correction. This was followed by neighbor-count filtering and region-growing to remove unwanted points, improving the extraction of road markings from the point cloud. However, point-cloud density decreases and intensity quality degrades with increasing range, sensor settings, vehicle speed, and MMS hardware limitations. Additionally, lane markings may be partially or fully occluded by surrounding traffic, leading to missing points and making lane-marker extraction difficult when relying solely on point clouds. To enhance lane-mapping accuracy, the fusion of point-cloud data with MMS imagery is therefore introduced.

[51] Automatic detection of zebra crossings from mobile LiDAR data.

The study presents a fully automatic procedure for identifying zebra crossings from mobile LiDAR data. First road surfaces

TABLE X
SUMMARY ON LANE DETECTION ALGORITHM [47]

Method	Key Features	Approach	Advantages / Limitations
Voxel-based Upward Growing	Connectivity along vertical axis, Elevation	The point cloud is first divided into grid cells on the XY plane. From each cell, voxels are grown upward by merging with adjacent occupied cells until no further connections exist. The voxel with the maximum height is then evaluated against a threshold to classify points as either ground or non-ground.	Works well in uneven terrain. May struggle with noisy data.
Ground Segmentation	Height differences	Divide input into blocks, then cluster voxels with similar vertical statistics. Identify largest cluster as ground. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is used to classify the closest voxel as ground.	Efficient for simple scenes, scalable to larger areas.
Trajectory-Based Filter	Trajectory data and geo-referenced 2D imagery.	Filter points using trajectory and distance data. Rasterize filtered points onto a horizontal plane and compute voxel-based features. Combine binary images via logical operations to remove ground points.	Suitable for high-density point clouds. Rasterization may lead to over-segmentation.
Terrain Filter	Point density, Euclidean distance	Partition point cloud into horizontal grids, select representative points for local plane estimation, and define bounding boxes. Points outside the box are off-terrain. Iteratively group off-terrain points.	Handles complex scenes. Computationally intensive and time-consuming.
Voxel-Based Ground Removal	Elevation, Point density	Segment points into vertical voxels of uniform size. Remove voxels whose elevation is below a threshold.	Efficient and simple. Works best for areas with minor terrain variations.
RANSAC-Based Filter	Trajectory data, Height deviation	Divide cloud along trajectory and fit planes via RANSAC. Iteratively refine by comparing point elevation with fitted plane.	Fast and effective in single-plane scenes. Not ideal for complex, multi-plane terrain.

TABLE XI
COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW OF LANE MARKING EXTRACTION TECHNIQUES [47]

Category	Method	Input Features	Strengths	Limitations
2D Image-Based Methods	Adaptive Multi-Threshold Segmentation	Pixel intensity, reflectance contrast, contextual cues	Handles illumination variation; Simple implementation; Suitable for structured roads	Sensitive to worn markings; Performance drops in cluttered scenes
	Hough Transform-Based Detection	Edge maps, grayscale intensity	Computationally efficient; Effective for straight lines	Limited for curved or complex symbols; Affected by occlusions
	Multi-Scale Tensor Voting	Intensity gradients, spatial continuity	Preserves linear structures; Suppresses noise	Parameter tuning required; Higher computational cost
3D MLS-Based Methods	Deep Neural Network Models	3D point clouds, reflectivity, geometric descriptors	High accuracy; Learns complex spatial patterns	Requires large labeled datasets; High training cost
	Profile-Based Intensity Analysis	Laser intensity, scan angle, trajectory data	Efficient for large-scale datasets; No predefined lane model needed	Sensitive to reflectance variation; Less robust in rural roads

are segmented through a curvature-based analysis applied to each LiDAR scan cycle, which isolates the pavement region for further processing. The extracted road points are then transformed into intensity-based raster images, enabling subsequent use of 2D image-processing techniques. Zebra-crossing candidates are detected using the Standard Hough Transform, guided by geometric constraints that reflect the typical arrangement of zebra stripes.

To improve detection reliability, several classical image-processing steps are employed: binarization to separate markings from pavement, median filtering to suppress noise, and morphological operations to close small gaps and refine the stripe boundaries. After the marking pattern is isolated, its spatial position is computed for integration into geographic information systems relevant to road inventory and maintenance workflows. Experimental results across 30 zebra crossings showed a success rate of 83%, with missed

detections linked to worn paint or occlusions from vehicles in the point cloud.

[52] Extraction of road lane markings from mobile LiDAR data

This study proposes an approach for identifying lane markings using point-cloud data collected by mobile LiDAR systems. The approach utilizes intensity information and geometric characteristics of the scanned surface to distinguish pavement markings from surrounding road surfaces. Filtering and segmentation are applied to enhance marking visibility and improve detection accuracy under varying surface conditions.

Lane markings extraction based on Machine learning methods:

[53] Intensity Thresholding and Deep Learning Based Lane Marking Extraction and Lane Width Estimation

from Mobile Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) Point Clouds

The work outlines two different strategies for lane-marking extraction from mobile LiDAR data. The first relies on an enhanced intensity-thresholding technique supported by an unsupervised normalization step, while the second employs a deep-learning model trained using automatically generated labels. The normalized thresholding method enhances the stability of intensity values and improves lane marking detection compared to traditional thresholding, while the deep learning approach achieves even higher accuracy and extracts more continuous lane segments across both asphalt and concrete pavements. The extracted markings are further used for estimating lane widths and identifying missing or degraded lane marking regions.

[54] Transfer Learning for LiDAR-Based Lane Marking Detection and Intensity Profile Generation

This paper presents a transfer learning framework designed to reduce the large data requirements typically associated with LiDAR-based deep learning models for lane marking detection. U-Net model was originally trained on two-lane highway data, then fine-tune it using only a small number of samples from new target datasets with different road patterns. Their experiments compare encoder-focused and decoder-focused fine-tuning strategies and show that updating only the encoder yields superior performance, achieving F1-scores up to 86.9% on target data and 90.1% on an independent dataset. Using the lane markings extracted by the fine-tuned model, authors also generate intensity profiles to identify worn or missing lane markings. This approach demonstrates that effective lane marking detection can be achieved with minimal new training data.

[55] Segmentation and classification of road markings using MLS data

The study presents a structured workflow designed to extract and classify road markings from mobile laser scanning (MLS) point-cloud data. Their approach begins by isolating highly reflective road-surface points and organizing them into an intensity image. Within this representation, local orientation cues are used to cluster pixels with similar angular patterns, forming masks that highlight potential marking regions. For each of these masked areas, Otsu's adaptive thresholding is applied to separate marking points from the surrounding pavement. The segmented features are then grouped into individual marking elements, which are subsequently classified into semantic categories such as pedestrian crossings and directional arrows using a neural-network-based classifier. This combination of geometric filtering, adaptive segmentation, and machine-learning-based classification enables accurate detection and labeling of common road marking types in MLS data.

[56] K-Lane: Lidar Lane Dataset and Benchmark for Urban Roads and Highways

A new LiDAR-based lane dataset, KAIST-Lane, is introduced along with a lane-detection framework called LLDN-GFC, which extracts lane lines in the bird's-eye-view (BEV) domain. Two variants of this model are presented: Proj28-GFC-T3, which uses a 28-layer point-projection encoder with three Transformer blocks, and Pillars-GFC-M5, which employs a pillar-based encoder combined with five Mixer blocks. The study compares the performance of LLDN-GFC against CNN-based LLDN models, particularly under scenarios where lane markings are partially occluded. This technique operate robustly under various lighting conditions.

[57] Using deep learning to digitize road arrow markings from LIDAR point cloud derived images

This study introduces a deep-learning method to automatically detect and convert road-arrow markings into digital map features using images derived from LiDAR point clouds. The LiDAR data is transformed into 2D images, which are then processed with a U-Net segmentation model to identify arrow markings. The segmented results are mapped back to their real-world coordinates, allowing the system to extract accurate polygon and polyline shapes. These shapes are exported as vector shapefiles for use in high-definition (HD) mapping. The performance levels of this approach is comparable to existing methods.

[58] A deep learning framework for road marking extraction, classification and completion from mobile laser scanning point clouds

The paper presents a comprehensive learning-based system for extracting, classifying, and completing road markings from Mobile Laser Scanning (MLS) LiDAR point clouds. A modified U-Net architecture is utilized to identify and segment road-marking pixels, followed by a CNN-based hierarchical classifier to distinguish different marking types. To address missing or fragmented markings, the method integrates a GAN-based completion module, producing more complete and reliable outputs. The framework is trained on a custom MLS road-marking dataset and demonstrates strong performance across diverse environments, outperforming traditional intensity-based approaches.

[59] Advancements in 3d lane detection using lidar point clouds: From data collection to model development

LiLaDet is a LiDAR-based 3D lane-detection framework designed to address the challenges posed by sparse point-cloud data and the lack of comprehensive annotated datasets. The authors introduce LiSV-3DLane, a large-scale surround-view LiDAR dataset containing 20,000 frames with detailed semantic lane annotations, providing full 360-degree coverage of urban and highway environments. Using this dataset, the paper proposes LiLaDet, a model that leverages the geometric structure of lane markings and transforms LiDAR data into a Bird's-Eye View (BEV) representation for accurate 3D lane estimation. Experimental evaluations show that LiLaDet surpasses both existing LiDAR-based and camera-based

baselines on the K-Lane and LiSV-3DLane benchmarks, demonstrating its effectiveness in real-world traffic scenarios.

[60]LLFormer4D: LiDAR-based lane detection method by temporal feature fusion and sparse transformer

Authors introduced LLFormer4D, a LiDAR-based lane detection framework that integrates temporal feature fusion with a sparse Transformer architecture. The method processes sequential point cloud data to enhance robustness and continuity in dynamic driving environments. A convolutional backbone extracts spatial features, while a sparse Transformer decoder models long-range dependencies efficiently. By incorporating multi-frame information, the approach improves lane structure consistency compared to single-frame methods. The framework is designed to handle complex urban scenarios and varying environmental conditions. Experimental results demonstrate improved detection accuracy and stability, highlighting the effectiveness of Transformer-based deep learning for 3D LiDAR lane perception.

[61]BoostedDim attention: A novel data-driven approach to improving LiDAR-based lane detection

The BoostedDim Attention framework improves LiDAR-based lane detection by refining how Vision Transformer models handle sparse point-cloud features. It enhances Multi-Head Self-Attention within the K-Lane baseline, enabling better geometric feature extraction under challenging scenarios such as nighttime, unknown conditions at short ranges (0–30m), and daytime at longer ranges (30–50m). The authors introduce distance-aware metrics—True Positive Rate (TPR) and Lateral Error—that more accurately capture performance variations tied to LiDAR range and driving conditions. Their analysis highlights the importance of calibrated reflectivity and intensity data: intensity improves detection in low-light short-range settings but can hinder performance in bright daytime long-range scenarios, emphasizing adaptive feature use. Overall, BoostedDim Attention provides a more robust attention mechanism customized for LiDAR inputs, yielding stronger lane-detection reliability and offering valuable direction for advancing autonomous-driving perception.

[62]LaneCorrect: Self-supervised Lane Detection

LaneCorrect is a self-supervised lane-detection framework developed to eliminate dependence on manually labeled training data. LiDAR point-cloud intensity is used to isolate lane structures through unsupervised 3D segmentation, taking advantage of how lane markings appear distinctly in LiDAR scans. These 3D lane points are then projected onto 2D images to form initial pseudo-labels, which tend to be noisy. To improve their quality, the authors introduce a self-supervised correction network that learns geometric consistency and instance-level information under adversarial augmentations. A distilled student model is then trained using the corrected labels, enabling the system to generalize to standard lane-detection datasets such as TuSimple and CULane without human annotations. Extensive evaluations

Fig. 4. Road lane detection on 3D LIDAR data with the usage of reflectivity of points.

across multiple benchmarks show that LaneCorrect achieves accuracy comparable to supervised methods and displays stronger robustness to domain shifts, such as training on CULane and testing on TuSimple. LaneCorrect demonstrates how combining LiDAR-driven pseudo-labeling with self-supervised learning can create scalable, annotation-free lane-detection systems for autonomous driving.

[63]Flexible 3D Lane Detection via Hierarchical Shape Matching

This paper presents a deep learning framework for detecting complex 3D lane geometries from point cloud data. The method introduces a hierarchical representation that captures both global lane structures and local geometric variations, enabling flexible modeling of curved and irregular lane layouts. A shape-matching strategy is employed to align predicted lane representations with ground truth annotations, improving structural consistency. The network integrates multi-level feature extraction with dynamic matching mechanisms to enhance robustness in challenging driving scenarios. Experimental evaluations demonstrate improved accuracy in capturing lane topology compared to conventional regression-based approaches.

VII. AN EXAMPLE OF ROAD LANE MARKING DETECTION USING LiDAR DATA

Fig. 4 shows an example of road lane detection with LiDAR data, and steps involved are explained in brief below.

1) *Interpolate intensity values for the points on the ground plane:* Given intensity values are interpolated between 0-255 using:

$$I_{Int} = I_{Imin} + \frac{O_{Imax} - O_{Imin}}{I_{Imax} - I_{Imin}} * (I_{IVal} - I_{Imin}) \quad (18)$$

Where, I_{IVal} is the input I_{Int} is interpolated value.

TABLE XII
SOME USEFUL LINKS

Topics	Relevant links
laser basics	Lasers: Understanding the basics
Laser diodes	Beginner guide laser diodes
Literature on basics	[65]
More details on file formats	File formats for machine learning
.h5 file	doc hdf5 py video paper
.bin file	refDoc CarlaFormat Intro Details
.pcd format	Tutorial Explanation
.bin data type to .pcd in python	.bin to .pcd format
.las documentation	lasFiles
.pkl files	pkl documentation
.pcap	pcapDoc
Velodyne	Velodyne LiDAR user manual
TI manual	Automotive LiDAR TI Manual
Different ways to process LiDAR data	Data Processing Whitebox
Veloview	veloview1 veloview2
LidarView	lidarview
Velodyne LiDAR teardown	VelodyneTeardown

I_{Imin} and I_{Imax} are minimum and maximum observed intensity values

O_{Imin} and O_{Imax} are 0 and 255 respectively.

2) *Surface Normal estimation:* [64] The estimation of a surface-point normal is formulated as a least square fitting problem. This method is essentially the same as approximating the normal vector of a plane that is tangent to the surface.

A covariance matrix is constructed using the nearest-neighbor points surrounding the query point, and the solution is reduced to an analysis of the eigenvalues and eigenvectors(or PCA – Principal Component Analysis). for each point p_i , the covariance matrix is assembled as :

$$C = \frac{1}{k} \sum (p_i - p) \cdot (p_i - p)^T, C \cdot v_j = \lambda_j \cdot v_j, j \in 0, 1, 2 \quad (19)$$

Here, k represents the number of neighboring points around p_i , The term p denotes the 3D centroid of these neighbors, The value λ_j is the j^{th} eigenvalue of the covariance matrix, and v_j the j^{th} eigenvector. To ensure that all surface normals n consistently face the viewpoint, they are oriented such that the condition $n \cdot (v_p - p_i) > 0$ is satisfied.

3) *Calculate incident angle:* Incident angle is calculated as a dot product of point location and surface normal at that point.

4) *Calculate reflectivity:*

$$R = I \frac{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)}{\cos(\theta_{inc})} \quad (20)$$

Where, R- reflectivity

x,y,z - position of the point

θ_{inc} - Incident angle.

A. Some existing implementation/ Manuals/References

Links to multiple references are listed in XII.

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